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Effectiveness of Instructional Materials in Teaching and Learning of Letter-Word Recognition among Out-of-School Children in Kaduna: A Literature Review

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Abstract

It is very important to note that, the use of instructional materials is virtually necessary. This paper focused on qualitative study on Instructional Materials: Panacea for Effective Teaching and Learning of Letter-Word Recognition among Out-Of-School Children in Kaduna. The paper investigated the concept of out-of-school children and the concept of instructional materials. It looked into the importance of instructional materials in teaching and learning classification of instructional materials and their relevance to the teaching of letter-word recognition to the out-of-school children. The study discussed the criteria for guiding the selection of instructional materials to teach the out-of-school children. It highlighted the steps to be followed when using instructional materials to teach the out-of-school children. The paper provided the following areas as suggestions based on the conversations that have already taken place in this study in order to encourage instructors of out-of-school children to adopt the attitude of employing instructional resources. It maintained that education resource centers organize seminars to teach language instructors, and to evaluate students' learning proficiency outside of the classroom primarily in the north. Educational stakeholders should ensure the provision of instructional materials for daily letter-word recognition and to enhance visual-motor abilities in letter recognition for children not in school.

Keywords: instructional, material, letter-word, out-of-school, school-children

Introduction

Education has always been the cornerstone of all lasting national advancements. It is the tool that starts the race for optimal development, progress, and problem-solving across all sectors. Education must engage everyone and be successfully taught for it to be relevant in a nation (Alipour, 2014). All of these goals can only be reached by using effective teaching strategies and age-appropriate instructional resources when working with out-of-school children (Coomb, 2010). This study's focus is on the teaching materials and how they apply to children who are not in school. Because out-of-school children encounter these resources but are unaware that they aid in learning, it is necessary to make educating them practical through the use of instructional materials. In order to identify words and swiftly access their meanings, Out-of-School Children that should use effective word-recognition strategies are able to quickly and automatically transform the letters or spelling patterns of written words into spoken sounds (Vandervelden & Siegel, 1997). To focus on the meaning of what they are reading, Out-of-School Children should need to be able to rapidly and easily recognize words (Stanovich, 1986). Effective word-identification techniques will enable such children to deduce the pronunciations of words they have never seen in print as they get older and read increasingly complex books. It is critical that Out-of-School Children may learn to recognize words primarily by using their sound and spelling skills (Bay Area Reading Task Force, 1997; Beck, 1998). The chance to engage with bigger units, such as word families, spelling patterns, and onsets and rimes, should also be provided to Out-of-School Children. More complex word-identification techniques concentrate on reading multisyllabic words and structural analysis, which includes identifying root words, prefixes, and suffixes. Before they can sound out some basic words (like this and the), Out-of-School Children may be able to recognize them. It is important to educate Out-of-School Children how to use word-identification procedures to figure out words, even if some words are only presented as sight words. According to research by Smith et al. (in press) and Stein, Johnson, & Gutlohn (1998), there was insufficient representation in word recognition training and oral language skills instruction for Out-of-School Children. According to Stein et al., very few programs used an explicit phonics approach, and the majority of Out-of-School Children reading selections were inaccessible to them because they frequently did not match the terms that Out-of-School Children were learning during word-recognition training.

Although the word-recognition instruction to reading achievement is a much-debated topic, any enlightened discussion by advocates of such instruction emphasizes that it must be only a part of a total program of instruction (Snow, Bums, & Griffin, 1998). The main goal of such instruction is to help Out-of-School Children figure out the alphabetic system of written English and become comfortable with that system as they become readers (Lyon, 1998). The authors of *Becoming a Nation of Readers* (Anderson, Hiebert, Scott, & Wilkinson, 1985), written almost a decade ago, nicely described the goal, purpose, and limitations

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of phonics instruction: While there is substantial dispute regarding the relationship between reading achievement and systematic phonics and word-recognition training for Out-of-School Children (Snow, Bums, & Griffin, 1998). As Out-of-School Children become readers, the primary objective of this kind of training is to assist them in understanding the alphabetic system of written English and help them grow accustomed to it (Lyon, 1998).

Concept of Out-of-School Children

Children who are not enrolled in any school or who have left school at any point before finishing elementary education are considered out of school children (OoSC) (Aremu, 2008). Children who are not in school are quite diverse. Children who are living or working in urban areas, on streets, on railroad platforms, or on construction sites are examples of children who are not enrolled in school (Out-of-School Children). This category of learners might be employed as street hawkers, housekeepers, child laborers, wage employees, mechanics, rag pickers, or shoe shine boys. Other categories might include children involved in the sex trade, children whose parents move around in search of seasonal work, children from scheduled castes and tribes, children with special needs who may fall into any of these categories, and children who suffer disadvantage due to socio-cultural, economic, geographic, and linguistic factors. In addition to these, there are kids who attend minority community-run Madarasas (Islamic Education) for their education and study religious texts with little to no involvement in the standard curriculum. In a similar vein, there may be teenage females who have never attended school or who may have left early. Children who live in troubled neighborhoods or in challenging situations must also be found and supported in neighborhood schools. In order to close the achievement gaps and integrate these diverse groups of children into the general education system in the age-appropriate classrooms, specific efforts must be made to expose them to instructional materials (Wales, 2012).

The Concept of Instructional Materials

Instructional resources, educational technology, instructional technology, etc. are all terms used to describe instructional materials. In education, instructional materials are anything that a teacher uses during teaching to improve the learning process (Smith, 2009). According to Ehri & McCormick (1998), instructional materials are any hardware, software, or group of resources that teachers can use to facilitate teaching, learning, and leaving. Additionally, according to Aremu (2008), instructional materials are those that help teachers do their jobs more effectively and efficiently while also reducing the stress associated with teaching and learning for both the teachers and the students. Thus, children will play with letters and word games, and begin to learn how the system of print works. Here, they may begin to understand that the teacher read print from left to right, from the top of the page to the bottom, that capital letters begin sentences, that periods end sentences, and more. For that awareness of these concepts of print provides the backdrop against which reading or writing are acquired

Importance of Instructional materials in teaching and learning

The value of instructional materials lies in how they enhance learning by making it more engaging, applicable, and appealing (Stanovich, 1986). Additionally, they make it possible for both professors and students to actively and productively engage in class. According to Aremu (2008), instructional materials encourage active learning among students during the teaching and learning process. He added that it spares instructors' time and effort. Wales (2012) also noted that the use of instructional materials by instructors' aids in their efficient performance of their jobs. According to Smith, the value of instructional materials is that they facilitate learning for students by making information clearer, more vivid, and more engaging. The use of instructional resources, according to Coomb (2010), is advantageous to both the instructor and the student. This is because they allow teachers to care for each student's unique differences while also saving them time and energy. They particularly assist kids who lack certain abilities. The aforementioned ideas have demonstrated the critical significance instructional materials have in the teaching and learning processes of out-of-school children. For Aremu (2008); & Wales (2012), the following list of factors illustrates the significance of educational resources for a child who is not in school:

1. Instructional materials can encourage meaningful communication of interest among out-of-school children, which in turn facilitates efficient learning.
2. The use of instructional materials can strengthen retentive memory because the out-of-school child can readily see and observe which increases the rate of remembering.
3. Non-schooled children might be inspired to learn quickly by instructional materials.
4. For these children who are not in school, it can quickly facilitate the necessary target.

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5. The difficulty for the out-of-school children will decrease.
6. The use of instructional materials for educating the out-of-school children facilitates exposure to practical tasks.

Aremu (2008); & Wales (2012) elucidated that reading and writing instruction that focuses on the use and appreciation of written language includes activities that help out-of-school children to understand that print represents spoken language; to highlight the meanings, uses, and production of print found in classroom signs, labels, notes, posters, calendars, and directions; learn print conventions, such as directionality; to practice how to handle a book - how to turn pages, how to find the tops and bottoms of pages, and how to tell the front and back covers. Here, the lessons in word awareness will help out-of-school children to become conscious of individual words (e.g., their boundaries, their appearance, and their length).

Classification of Instructional Materials and their Relevance to the Teaching of Letter-Word Recognition to the Out-of-School Children

Wales (2012), classified Instructional materials into three: the audio, the visual and audio-visual Instructional materials.

Audio Materials

These are those instructional items that a teacher brings to class but that only the students can hear. They are instructional materials that exclusively appeal to the sense of hearing; they don't display images or produce motion. Radio, tape recorders, telephones, and other audio devices are examples of resources that some youngsters who are not in school are most familiar with.

Visual Materials

These may be characterized as the instructional tools that the instructor uses and that the student sees and notices. They are instructional resources that convey information to students primarily via visual means. The teaching of letter-word recognition can be done through a variety of visual materials. These consist of tangible items, written documents, images, fees, maps, globes, etc. All of these can be utilized to teach letter-word recognition to children who are not enrolled in school. For instance, printed alphabet cards can be employed as instructional materials to teach letter-word recognition. Names of streets, towns, and nations can be taught via maps and globes. Images of various species can be used to illustrate words. Because, listening skill is a major component of many classroom tasks that is essential to incorporate audio instructional resources into the process of teaching letter-word recognition. In addition to audio resources, a teacher may also employ audio-visual elements in the classroom, which may be seen and heard. They simultaneously engage the senses of sight and sound. According to studies, students only retain 10% of what they read, 20% of what they hear, and 50% of what they see and hear (Wales, 2012). This shows that the use of audio-visual instructional materials is crucial when teaching out-of-school students and would have a greater impact on them because out-of-school students are exposed to these materials in one way or another without being aware of their educational value.

Films, videos, television, computers, and other forms of audio-visual media are examples. Children who are not in school can learn letter-word recognition using audio-visual instructional resources (Mougbamiam, Rivera, & Francis, 2009). For instance, letters, words, and what they visually represent can be taught via video tape cassette on a television or a CD on a computer. Children who are not enrolled in school can readily internalize and envision a film that demonstrates the steps involved in teaching letter-word recognition or the linguistic alphabet for use in the future (Aremu, 2008).

Criteria for Guiding the Selection of Instructional Materials to Teaching the Out-of-School Children

It is important to note that not all instructional resources can be used in a class of out-of-school students, and this relates to the guiding principles that teachers might apply when choosing materials to educate this group of students (Mougbamiam, Rivera, & Francis, 2009). Therefore, the instructor in a letter-word recognition class must ensure that the instructional material he chooses meets the learning demands of these different types of students. The instructional resources may only be made applicable to the teaching process through this approach. When choosing instructional materials, Aremu (2008) suggests that a language instructor should take into account three factors.

1. The instructional materials' adequacy and appropriateness. This implies that the language instructor must ensure that the teaching materials are appropriate for the age of the out-of-school students as well as the topic being taught (letter-word recognition). If instructional materials do not meet the learners' expectations, they will not be effective. Additionally, it will be meaningless if the course materials have nothing to do with the topic or problem that has to be addressed.
2. Learning materials need to be appealing, transportable, and adaptable. These characteristics increase the instructional materials' relevance and efficiency when used to teach these varieties. Additionally, they design the instructional materials

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to be simple for the instructor to manipulate. If instructional materials are not made appealing, they may lose their worth or credibility in terms of stimulating the attention of children who are not in school.

3. The cost of the instructional materials must be planned for. The language instructor should make every effort to suggest and recommend instructional materials that the management of these classes of learners can pay since the instructional materials should be appropriate for the students' age levels.

Steps to be Followed when Using Instructional Materials to Teach the Out-of-School Children

It is important to remember that teachers should follow specific guidelines while using instructional materials to teach children who are not enrolled in school. These actions would improve the efficient use of educational resources in the classroom. The stages should thus be followed by the language instructor to ensure that the goal of employing instructional materials is successfully attained. Aremu (2008); & Mougbamiam, Rivera, & Francis (2009) concurred in maintaining steps that a language teacher should employ when using instructional materials to teach the out-of-school children through the following steps:

1. **Preparation:** This means that children who need training (teaching) should be identified by the teacher and the school management committee run by the relevant government, and such training should be organized as follows:
 - a) The instructional materials must be well crafted, developmentally appropriate learning materials that have been approved by the academic authority (syllabus).
 - b) Classes for the aforementioned letter-word recognition instruction must be held in secure residential facilities or on school grounds.
 - c) (c.) The length should be for a time that may be extended based on the stakeholder of the instructional presentation's evaluation of the learning process.
2. **Preparing the instructional Materials:** The language instructor is now expected to carefully review the instructional resources to ensure that they are complete, intact, and prepared for usage with these kinds of learners.
3. **Preparing the environment:** The language instructor is responsible for making sure that the area where the instructional materials will be utilized is free from distracting noise when using audio and audio-visual resources, and that the area is accident-free while utilizing language laboratories.
4. **Preparing the students:** Placement conditions are involved; in other words, since out-of-school children are of varying ages, the instructor must ensure that age-matched pairs are seated in order to achieve acts of preparedness.
5. **Evaluating the Instructional materials:** This draws the language teacher's attention to the need to ensure that the instructional materials used to teach letter-word recognition are accurate and pertinent to the needs of students who are not currently enrolled in school.

Conclusion

The discussions in this study have focused on the value of instructional materials in imparting letter-word recognition to youngsters who are not enrolled in school. The conversations made it abundantly evident that instructional materials not only offer a tangible foundation for conceptual thinking, but also boost the learning interest and permanence of learning in out-of-school children, encouraging the development of their self-ability. This study has also made it quite evident that instructional resources must be used to teach letter-word recognition, just like they are for teaching any other component of English. The study found that every course geared at children who are not in school needs instructional resources and that there is no course for these learners without them. It is expected of the language teacher to introduce phonological awareness, decoding, and sight recognition to the youngsters who are not enrolled in school. Letter-word recognition becomes automatic as a result of the gradual integration of these talents. Letter identification is the simplest definition of letter recognition. Before they can name, write, or sound out the letters, it is one of the fundamental abilities that elementary school-aged children must possess.

Recommendations

The following elements are suggested based on the conversations that have already taken place in this study in order to encourage instructors of out-of-school children to adopt the attitude of employing instructional resources.

1. Education resource centers, primarily in the North, should plan for the enforce strategies to ensure adequate availability manufacture of instructional materials at all levels of education to teach the children who are not in school the letters in their names and give them a lot of practice.

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2. Seminars, workshops and Conferences for to teach language instructors should be organized consistently how to evaluate students' oral reading proficiency outside of the classroom.
3. With the provision in item one, daily letter-word recognition promotion and promotion of visual-motor abilities in letter recognition for children not in school.

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